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**STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCEMENT OF SKILL ACQUISITION FOR SELF EMPLOYMENT
AMONG STUDENTS OF ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE WORKS TRADE
IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN YOBE STATE**

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the Strategies for Enhancement of Skill Acquisition for Self-Employment among Students of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Yobe State, Nigeria. Three research questions were asked. The study which was conducted in Northeast Nigeria adopted survey research design. The population of the study was 176 people consisting of 29 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade teachers, 16 workshop attendants, and 131 industry supervisors in Yobe State. The sample size for the study was 176. The whole population sampling technique was employed. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: “Skill Acquisition for self-employment and Job-creation Enhancement Questionnaire (SASJEQ). Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.85 which is considered reliable. The findings further revealed that the key challenges that prevent students from acquiring skills that could help students to be self-employed and create job for others include inadequacy of curriculum, lack of hands-on training opportunities, lack of modern equipment, poor emphasis on safety protocols, inadequate duration of training program among other identified problems. These recommendations were made: The teaching strategies that should be used in Technical Colleges in Yobe State, Nigeria include hands-on practical demonstration, Regular workshop practical sessions, use of real-life scenario in teaching, interactive session, peer learning activities, incorporating multimedia resources, feedback from instructors’ practical tasks, opportunity for hands.

Keywords: Skill Acquisition, Self-Employment, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade

INTRODUCTION

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade is an essential vocational discipline taught in Technical Colleges across Nigeria. It equips students with the necessary skills and knowledge to work in the electrical industry, focusing on the installation, maintenance, and repair of electrical systems. According to the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2015), Technical Colleges in Nigeria offer comprehensive training programs in this trade to meet the demands of the construction, manufacturing, and infrastructure sectors. Students learn to read electrical blueprints, install wiring, troubleshoot faults, and ensure compliance with safety regulations. The curriculum also covers electrical theories, practical hands-on training, and the use of specialized tools and equipment. By providing quality education in Electrical Installation and

Maintenance Works Trade, Technical Colleges in Nigeria contribute significantly to the development of a skilled workforce capable of supporting the country's electrical infrastructure and industries. In the context of Technical Colleges in Nigeria, the Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade curriculum emphasizes a combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. It aims to produce competent electrical technicians capable of contributing to the growth of the nation's economy.

Skill acquisition refers to the process of obtaining and developing specific abilities, competencies, and knowledge that enable individuals to perform tasks effectively and efficiently in a particular domain. It involves learning practical skills through hands-on experiences, training, and education. Skill acquisition is crucial for personal development, employability, and economic growth. It encompasses a wide range of skills, including technical and vocational skills, cognitive skills, social and emotional skills, and problem-solving abilities (Kamala, 2020). Skill acquisition is not limited to formal education; it also involves informal learning, on-the-job training, and experiential learning, which are essential for adapting to changing work environments and societal demands (Tynjälä, 2013). Skill acquisition in Technical Colleges of Nigeria is a critical aspect of vocational education that aims to equip students with and employable skills in various trades. Technical Colleges play a crucial role in developing a skilled workforce that meets the demands of industries and contributes to national development (Owoyemi & Ogunbiyi, 2015).

Self-employment is a concept that emphasizes an individual's ability to create job for himself, meet his needs and achieve his goals independently, without relying on external support or assistance. It involves developing a sense of autonomy and self-sufficiency in various aspects of life, such as economic, social, and emotional well-being. According to Arogundade et al. (2018) self-employment is a critical skill that enables individuals to take charge of their lives, make informed decisions, and overcome challenges effectively. This concept is often associated with self-determination and empowerment, as individuals who are self-reliant have a higher sense of control over their circumstances and are better equipped to navigate through life's uncertainties.

Achieving self-employment requires the development of specific skills and competencies. Sule and Hassan (2019) argue that acquiring vocational skills and education plays a crucial role in promoting self-reliance. Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade equips individuals with practical skills and knowledge that can lead to self-employment or gainful employment, empowering them to generate income and support themselves. Additionally, self-reliance is closely linked to financial literacy and entrepreneurial skills (Ogundele et al., 2021). Understanding financial management, budgeting, and investment enables individuals to make sound financial decisions and build sustainable livelihoods. Overall, self-reliance is a multifaceted concept that encompasses a sense of independence, self-confidence, and the ability to take charge of one's destiny.

To ensure the success of skill acquisition programs, collaboration between Technical Colleges and the private sector is essential. Industries in Yobe State should actively engage with Technical Colleges by providing mentorship, internships, and job placement opportunities for students. Such partnerships can facilitate knowledge transfer and expose students to the realities of the job market, helping them develop skills that are relevant and in demand. Additionally, the government of Yobe State should invest in infrastructure and facilities in Technical Colleges to create a conducive learning environment. Adequate resources and modern equipment will enable students to acquire the latest technical skills and keep pace with industry advancements. Ultimately, the enhancement of skill acquisition for Self-employment among students of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Yobe State will not only empower the youth but also contribute to

the overall development of the state. It is against this backdrop that this study intends to provide strategies for enhancing skill acquisition for self-employment among students of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Yobe State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Enhancement of skill acquisition for self-employment and job creation among students of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Yobe State" revolves around the need to address the challenges faced by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in acquiring relevant skills for self-reliance in the state. Adeyemo and Adedokun (2021) emphasize that there is a gap between the skills taught in technical colleges and the actual demands of the job market. Moreover, the lack of modern equipment and infrastructure in technical colleges may impede skill development among students. Ibrahim and Saidu (2020) argue that many technical colleges in Yobe State suffer from inadequate resources and outdated facilities, limiting students' exposure to cutting-edge technologies. Without access to modern equipment and tools, students may not fully grasp the practical aspects of electrical installation and maintenance works. This research work seeks to identify the appropriate strategies that could use to enhance skill acquisition for self-employed in Technical Colleges in Yobe State, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to:

1. Determine the teaching strategies that could be used to enhance Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment.
2. Determine the supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment.
3. Determine the assessment strategies that could be used to enhance Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the teaching strategies that could be used to enhanced Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment?
2. What are the supervisory strategies that could be used to enhanced Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment?
3. What are the assessment strategies that could be used to enhanced Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students' skill acquisition for self-employment?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This review discussed under the following subheadings: Theoretical Framework, Teaching Strategies for Enhancing Students' Skill Acquisition for Self-employment, Supervisory Strategies for Enhancing Students' Skill Acquisition for Self-reliance and Assessment Strategies for Enhancing Students' Skill Acquisition for Self-reliance.

The study was hinged on Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, introduced in the 1977. At its core, the theory delves into the intricate interplay between observation, imitation, and the cultivation of self-efficacy. Bandura challenged

traditional behaviorist perspectives by highlighting the role of cognitive processes in learning, asserting that individuals learn not just through direct experience but also through observing others. This theoretical perspective has profound implications, particularly in the realm of skill acquisition for self-reliance and job creation. The key components of Social Cognitive Theory include, Observational Learning, Modeling and Imitation, Reciprocal Determinism, Self-Efficacy, and Cognitive Processes.

Teaching, according to Onabanjo (2020) is a deliberate effort by a mature or an experienced person to impart information, knowledge, skills and attitude to an immature or less experienced person through a process that is morally justified and skillful or knowledgeable in giving instruction. Onabanjo further stated that teaching as the technique for instruction and communication are categorized into instructor-centred, interactive, individualized and experimental and learner centred. Teaching is an attempt to assist students to acquire or change some skills, knowledge, idea and attitudes. Thus, teaching involves the setting up on activities to enable somebody learn something which can improve the person's knowledge, skills, attitude and values. Therefore, the aim of teaching is to facilitate learning.

The universal definition of supervisory skills, it is possible to draw upon various academic and professional sources to provide an encompassing understanding. According to Mintzberg (2019) a supervisor is a front-line manager that is on the ground and working alongside the employees. They typically oversee a group of subordinates to confirm tasks are complete, evaluate employee performance, identify needs, provide resources for employees to perform tasks, and work as an agent between staff and upper management. On the other hand, Supervisory skills refer to a set of abilities and competencies essential for individuals in leadership or managerial roles to effectively oversee and guide their teams. These skills are crucial for ensuring organizational success and employee satisfaction.

Assessment is about evaluating a student's work and making judgement about its performance. It is more than simply assigning a grade to a student. It reflects information on both teaching effectiveness and learning effectiveness: for instructors, it reflects academic achievement while for students it represents how much work and effort they can undertake. However, one fundamental aspect of assessment is to help students Learn from their assessed work and to improve their performance in future works. Thus, to enhance students' success, we believe that instructors should make use of different assessment strategies Trevena combination of assessment strategies based on the context and learning environment. To be able to best assess students, instructors also have to be aware of the strengths and weaknesses of each assessment strategy and its suitability.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), survey research design is a quantitative research method that involves collecting and analyzing data from a selected sample of individuals to draw conclusions about a larger population. Surveys typically use structured questionnaires or interviews to gather information on participants' attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016) this design allows researchers to generalize findings to a broader population, assess relationships between variables, and identify patterns or trends. The study was conducted in Yobe State of Nigeria. Yobe State, located in northeastern.

The target population for the study was 176 people consisting of 29 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade teachers, 16 workshop attendants, and 131 industry supervisors in Yobe State. The whole population was used, hence there was no sample. A structured questionnaire titled: "Skill Acquisition for self-employment and Job-creation Enhancement Questionnaire (SASJEQ) developed by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, SECTION A and B. Section A requests the demographic data of the respondents, which includes work status of the respondents as well as

department. Section B was further divided into eight (8) parts with each part dealing with the research question. Part I focused on determining the teaching strategies that could be utilized to enhance students' skill acquisition for self-employment. Part II delved into identifying supervisory strategies that could contribute to enhancing the skill acquisition of students for self-employment. Part III centered on determining assessment strategies that could aid in enhancing the skill acquisition of students for self-employment. The instrument was validated by two experts, to determine the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.85 which is considered reliable. Data that was gathered in the study was tabulated against each of the items of the instrument the statistical mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (SD) was used to analyze research questions. The mean of the responses was being calculated using 5-point Likert type scale as all responses with a 3.5 mean value was considered as “Agreed” and any item with a mean value less than 3.00 was considered as “Disagreed”.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the teaching strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation?

Table 1: Respondents' Mean and Standard Deviation on teaching strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation

S/N	Items	Supervisors (126)		Teachers (29)		W/Attend. (16)		Items Grand		Remark
		\bar{X}_1	σ_1	\bar{X}_2	σ_2	\bar{X}_3	σ_3	\bar{X}_G	σ_G	
1	Hands-on practical demonstration	4.17	1.03	3.79	1.47	3.88	1.50	4.08	1.16	Agreed
2	Regular workshop practical sessions	3.46	1.08	2.83	0.97	2.94	1.00	3.30	1.08	Agreed
3	Use of real-life scenario in teaching	4.12	0.88	4.17	1.31	4.44	1.09	4.16	0.98	Agreed
4	Interactive session	4.15	1.07	3.93	1.33	4.19	1.22	4.12	1.13	Agreed
5	Peer learning activities	4.26	0.96	4.45	0.69	4.44	0.73	4.31	0.90	Agreed
6	Incorporating multimedia resources	3.51	1.20	3.76	1.43	3.81	1.47	3.58	1.27	Agreed
7	Feedback from instructors on practical tasks	4.14	0.94	4.14	1.03	4.13	1.09	4.14	0.97	Agreed
8	Opportunity for hands-on practice outside regular class hours	3.87	1.15	4.45	0.69	4.44	0.73	4.02	1.08	Agreed
9	Encouragement to experiment with different techniques during practical session	3.93	1.27	4.38	0.90	4.56	0.73	4.06	1.19	Agreed
10	Provision of written manuals or guides	3.19	1.46	2.52	1.21	2.75	1.48	3.04	1.44	Agreed
11	Regular assessment of practical skills	3.23	1.43	2.55	1.21	2.25	1.29	3.02	1.42	Agreed
12	Collaborative projects with industry partners	3.60	1.37	3.97	1.18	4.06	1.18	3.71	1.33	Agreed
13	Availability of state-of-the art equipment	3.90	1.20	4.41	0.78	4.50	0.73	4.04	1.12	Agreed

14	Inclusion of safety training alongside technical instruction	2.87	1.39	4.28	0.92	4.44	0.81	3.25	1.43	Agreed
15	Opportunity for apprenticeship or internship in relevant industries	3.29	1.35	4.28	1.07	4.44	0.96	3.56	1.35	Agreed
16	Flexibility in learning schedules such as evening or weekend classes	3.50	1.43	4.31	0.97	4.38	0.96	3.72	1.37	Agreed
17	The provision of mentorship programs where experienced professionals guide students in practical skill development	3.87	1.14	4.14	1.03	4.13	1.09	3.94	1.12	Agreed
18	Regular updates to the curriculum to align with industrial standard	3.61	1.15	4.24	1.12	4.31	1.20	3.78	1.18	Agreed
19	Opportunities for hands-on troubleshooting exercise	3.18	1.45	2.28	1.49	2.25	1.57	2.94	1.51	Disagreed
20	Encouragement of self-directed learning or project development	2.83	1.36	2.76	1.48	2.50	1.63	2.78	1.40	Disagreed
		3.63	1.22	3.78	1.11	3.84	1.12	3.68	1.22	

\bar{X}_1 = Mean Rating of Supervisors, \bar{X}_2 = Mean Rating of Teachers, \bar{X}_3 = Mean Rating of Workshop Attendants, σ_1 = Standard Deviation for Supervisors' response, σ_2 = Standard Deviation for Teachers' response, σ_3 = Standard Deviation for Workshop Attendants' response, \bar{X}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation

Table 1 shows the mean responses and standard deviations of industries supervisors, teachers and workshop attendants on teaching strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The table revealed that 18 items (item 1 to 18) had their grand mean values ranging from 3.02 to 4.16 which are above the cut-off point of 3.00 indicating that the 18 items were agreed by the respondents as teaching strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. It can be deduced that the other two items (item 19 and 20) which had mean responses less than the 3.00 cut-off point were disagreed as teaching strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The grand standard deviation values ranged from 0.90 to 1.44. Each of the values is low; indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and to each other in their responses.

Research Question 2

What are the supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation?

Table 2: Respondents’ Mean and Standard Deviation on supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation

S/N	Items	Supervisors (126)		Teachers (29)		W/Attend. (16)		Items Grand		Remark
		\bar{X}_1	σ_1	\bar{X}_2	σ_2	\bar{X}_3	σ_3	\bar{X}_G	σ_G	
1	Clear instructions and guidance	3.10	1.33	3.14	1.25	2.81	1.11	3.08	1.29	Agreed
2	Encouragement of hands-on practice and experimentation	3.63	1.16	3.38	1.18	3.25	1.06	3.55	1.16	Agreed
3	Regular Constructive feedback on work performance	2.15	1.16	2.21	0.94	2.31	1.20	2.18	1.12	Disagreed
4	A supportive learning environment that encourages asking questions and seeking clarification	3.02	1.49	3.38	0.94	3.38	1.15	3.12	1.39	Agreed
5	Demonstration of proper techniques and best practices	3.25	1.46	3.28	1.00	4.38	1.02	3.36	1.39	Agreed
6	Assignment of tasks that helps to develop new skills	3.02	1.34	2.72	1.31	2.50	1.51	2.92	1.36	Disagreed
7	Motivation to learn and improve skills	3.22	1.51	3.17	0.85	3.56	0.89	3.25	1.37	Agreed
8	Facilitating opportunities for independent work on projects	3.10	1.55	2.21	1.32	2.25	1.44	2.87	1.54	Disagreed
9	Emphasis on importance of safety protocols and procedures	3.71	1.26	3.52	1.48	3.44	1.55	3.65	1.32	Agreed
10	Encouraging collaboration and teamwork among students	2.79	1.34	3.24	0.74	3.50	0.63	2.93	1.23	Disagreed
11	Provision of resources such as manuals, diagrams, and tools	3.22	1.53	2.38	1.50	2.19	1.42	2.98	1.56	Disagreed
12	Help and support readily available when students encounter difficulties	3.25	1.51	3.55	0.78	3.38	0.62	3.31	1.35	Agreed
13	Promotion of growth mindset, encouraging students to embrace challenges and learn from mistakes	3.78	1.08	3.83	1.47	3.94	1.48	3.80	1.19	Agreed
14	Setting of clear goals and objective for skill development	3.61	1.23	3.93	1.33	4.19	1.22	3.72	1.26	Agreed
15	Adapting teaching methods by supervisor to suit different learning styles among students	3.17	1.42	3.28	0.88	3.31	0.70	3.20	1.29	Agreed
16	Students feeling valued and respected by supervisor	4.12	1.08	4.07	1.19	4.19	1.17	4.12	1.10	Agreed
17	Emphasis on importance of continuous learning and professional development	4.13	1.00	3.90	1.26	4.13	1.15	4.09	1.06	Agreed
18	Provision of timely and relevant guidance when students are learning new techniques or procedures	3.98	1.15	4.24	0.87	4.38	0.81	4.06	1.09	Agreed
19	Provision of opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge to practical tasks	4.03	1.01	4.21	0.98	4.31	0.87	4.09	0.99	Agreed
20	Effective use of strategies to enhance skill acquisition for self-employment	4.13	0.97	4.17	1.07	4.25	1.00	4.15	0.99	Agreed
Grand		3.42	1.28	3.39	1.12	3.48	1.10	3.42	1.25	Agreed

\bar{X}_1 = Mean Rating of Supervisors, \bar{X}_2 = Mean Rating of Teachers, \bar{X}_3 = Mean Rating of Workshop Attendants, σ_1 = Standard Deviation for Supervisors’ response, σ_2 = Standard Deviation for Teachers’ response, σ_3 = Standard Deviation for Workshop Attendants’ response, \bar{X}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation.

Table 2 shows the mean responses and standard deviations of industries supervisors, teachers and workshop attendants on supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The table revealed that 16 items (item 1,2, 4,5, 7,9, and item 12 to 20) had their grand mean values ranging from 3.08 to 4.15 which are above the cutoff point of 3.00 indicating that the 16 items were agreed by the respondents as supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. It can be deduced that the other five items (item 3,6,8,10 and 11) which had mean responses less than the 3.00 cut-off point were disagreed as supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The grand standard deviation values ranged from 0.99 to 1.56. Each of the values is low; indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and to each other in their responses.

Research Question 3

What are the assessment strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation?

Table 3: Respondents’ Mean and Standard Deviation on assessment strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students’ skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation

S/N	Items	Supervisors (126)		Teachers (29)		W/Attend. (16)		Items Grand		Remark
		\bar{X}_1	σ_1	\bar{X}_2	σ_2	\bar{X}_3	σ_3	\bar{X}_G	σ_G	
1.	Practical assessment	4.10	0.95	4.28	0.84	4.31	0.87	4.15	0.92	Agreed
2.	Simulated real-world scenario	3.70	1.25	4.17	0.76	4.13	0.62	3.82	1.15	Agreed
3.	Feedback provided during assessment	4.09	0.91	4.21	0.68	4.13	0.62	4.11	0.85	Agreed
4.	Peer assessment activities	4.27	0.71	4.41	0.98	4.25	1.18	4.29	0.81	Agreed
5.	Assessment incorporating troubleshooting tasks	4.06	0.93	4.48	0.78	4.56	0.73	4.18	0.91	Agreed
6.	Application of theoretical knowledge to practical skills	3.69	1.03	4.41	0.78	4.50	0.73	3.89	1.02	Agreed
7.	Constructive criticism from instructors during assessment	4.21	0.93	3.86	1.43	3.88	1.50	4.12	1.09	Agreed
8.	Assessment requiring independent research and application of new techniques	4.21	0.81	4.21	0.94	4.25	1.00	4.21	0.85	Agreed
9.	Regular self-assessment	4.27	0.77	4.31	0.97	4.44	0.89	4.29	0.82	Agreed
10.	Assessment emphasizing safety protocols and procedures	3.95	0.94	4.45	0.78	4.50	0.73	4.09	0.92	Agreed
11.	Collaborative projects as assessment tasks	4.16	1.00	4.24	0.95	4.38	0.89	4.19	0.98	Agreed
12.	Assessment including reflection components	4.09	0.90	4.34	0.94	4.44	0.89	4.16	0.91	Agreed
13.	Practical assessments that mimic real-world challenges	4.21	0.86	4.28	1.07	4.44	0.96	4.25	0.91	Agreed
14.	Continuous assessment throughout the course duration	4.03	1.01	4.41	0.82	4.56	0.73	4.15	0.97	Agreed
15.	Assessment incorporating technological advancements	4.02	0.99	4.48	0.87	4.56	0.81	4.15	0.97	Agreed
16.	Timely feedback on assessment	4.10	0.98	3.31	1.81	3.44	1.86	3.90	1.29	Agreed
17.	Assessment requiring innovation and creative problem –solving	4.22	0.86	4.10	1.11	4.31	1.01	4.21	0.92	Agreed
18.	Use of Variety of assessment methods	4.19	0.89	4.00	1.25	4.06	1.29	4.15	1.00	Agreed

19.	Assessment allowing for hands-on practice and experimentation	4.04	1.00	3.83	1.39	4.00	1.32	4.00	1.10	Agreed
20.	Assessment strategies used in this course effectively prepares students for self-employment	4.25	0.86	4.21	1.05	4.25	1.18	4.25	0.92	Agreed
		4.09	0.93	4.20	1.01	4.27	0.99	4.13	0.96	

\bar{X}_1 = Mean Rating of Supervisors, \bar{X}_2 = Mean Rating of Teachers, \bar{X}_3 = Mean Rating of Workshop Attendants, σ_1 = Standard Deviation for Supervisors' response, σ_2 = Standard Deviation for Teachers' response, σ_3 = Standard Deviation for Workshop Attendants' response, \bar{X}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation

Table 3 shows the mean responses and standard deviations of industries supervisors, teachers and workshop attendants on assessment strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The table revealed that all the 20 items (item 1 to 20) had their grand mean values ranging from 3.82 to 4.29 which are above the cutoff point of 3.00 indicating that all the items were agreed by the respondents as assessment strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation. The grand standard deviation values ranged from 0.81 to 1.29. Each of the values is low; indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and to each other in their responses.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study in research question 1 revealed that Out of 20 possible teaching strategies for enhancing EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment which were used for investigation, 18 were found to be usable. They include, among others hands-on practical demonstration, regular practical sessions, collaborative projects with industry partners, provision of mentorship programs, and use of real-life scenario, while 2 were found to be unsuitable, while 2 were found to be unsuitable. This is in line with a study carried out by Akpan (2019) who conducted a study titled "Examining the Impact of Practical Training on Skill Acquisition and self-reliance in Electrical Installation Students in cross river state." The research aimed to explore the influence of practical training on skill acquisition and self-reliance among students in Electrical Installation programs.

The findings of the study in research question 2 reveals that out of 20 possible supervisory strategies for enhancing EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment which were used for investigation, 15 were found to be usable. They include, among other, clear instruction and guidance, demonstration of proper techniques and best practices, and provision of opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge to practical tasks, while 5 were found to be unsuitable. This is in line with the research conducted by Tumba and Shuaibu (2019) to identify strategies for improving students' acquisition of practical skills in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade in technical colleges of Kano State with a view to finding out ways of optimizing practical skills acquisition among students, it was found out in the study that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of trade teachers and students on supervisory strategies for students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade in technical colleges of Kano State. The findings of the study include among others; Demonstration, assignment, drill and practice, and apprenticeship strategies as much appropriate for enhancing practical skills acquisition by students.

The findings of the study in research question 3 on assessment strategies for enhancing student's skill acquisition for self-employment and job creation, this study found out that, out of 20 possible assessment strategies for enhancing EIMWT students' skill acquisition for self-employment and job-creation which were used for investigation, all the 20 were found to be usable. They include, among others. Practical assessment, collaborative projects as assessment tasks, continuous

assessment throughout the course duration and use of variety assessment methods, this finding is in consonant with the study of Ishaya Tumba and Halliru Shuaibu (2016) who found out that there is no significant difference between the men responses of EIMW trade teachers and school administrators on the assessment strategies for practical skill acquisition in EIMWT, the assessment strategies included assessing students' practical lesson using checklist assessment strategies, giving project work to students every week, allowing students to participate in assessment process, giving different assignment to each student at the end of each lesson among others.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that insufficient hands-on practical training, gap between skill taught in the technical colleges and the skill needed in the job market, mismatch between the curriculum and industry requirement, lack of modern equipment and infrastructure, inadequate resources and outdated facilities are the challenges faced by students of science and technical colleges leading to underachievement of skill acquisition. The study also found some strategies that could be used to enhance skill acquisition for self-employment and job creation among EIMWT students in technical colleges in Yobe state, which include teaching strategies, supervisory strategies, assessment strategies, human relationship strategies, industry-college strategies, entrepreneurship education strategies, and information and communication technology (ICT) strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following are some recommendations of the study;

1. The teaching strategies that could be used to enhance Electrical Installation and Maintenance Wok student's skill acquisition for self-employment include utilization of hands-on practical demonstration, regular workshop practical sessions, use of real-life scenarios in teaching, interactive session where students actively participate in problem-solving.
2. The supervisory strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT student's skill acquisition for self-employment for clear instruction and guidance, regular constructive feedback on work performance, supportive learning environment, encouraging collaboration and teamwork among students, provision of timely and relevant guidance when students are learning new techniques or procedures among others.
3. The assessment strategies that could be used to enhance EIMWT student's skill acquisition for self-employment include practical assessment, simulated real-world scenarios in assessment.

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